

Table S1. Numbers of raw reads, cleaned reads, assembled contigs, PeSV-related contigs and number of variants identified for each of the two analyzed pomegranate samples.

Sample	Paired Reads	Trimmed and Cleaned Reads	Contigs ≥ 200	PeSV-Related Contigs	Recovered Variants
PS1	13,611,066	2,562,437	6,078	50	5
PS4	20,918,456	1,586,985	3,690	125	1

Table S2. Characteristics of the isolates and variants used in this study.

Isolate/Variant	Place of Origin	Symptoms	Amplified Region	Accession Number
PS1-1	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	complete genome	MT680930
PS1-2	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	complete genome	MT680931
PS1-3	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	complete genome	MT680932
PS1-4	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	complete genome	MT680933
PS1-5	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	complete genome	MT680934
PS4-1	Hatay-Turkey	Chlorotic rings	complete genome	MT680935
SRX2583192	China	Unknown	near complete genome	SRX2583192
SRX2735578	China	Unknown	6K1-3 end	SRX2735578
SRX2503675	India	Unknown	P3-3 end	SRX2503675
SRX2735578 3	China	Unknown	NIb-3 end	SRX2735578 3
SRX2735578 2	China	Unknown	6K1-3 end	SRX2735578 2
SRX2503675 2	India	Unknown	6K2-3 end	SRX2503675 2
SRX275580	China	Unknown	CP	SRX275580
SRX2503675 3	India	Unknown	CP	SRX2503675 3
225	Adana-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271616
228	Adana-Turkey	Mosaics, oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271617

229	Adana-Turkey	Vein clearing	CP	MT271618
231	Adana-Turkey	Light mosaics	CP	MT271619
232	Adana-Turkey	Mosaics, oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271620
239	Adana-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271621
241	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and mottling	CP	MT271622
242	Adana-Turkey	Vein clearing	CP	MT271623
243	Adana-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271624
245	Adana-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271625
247	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271626
226	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and mottlings	CP	MT271627
187	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns and heavy chlorotic spots	CP	MT271628
195	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and leaf deformation	CP	MT271629
201	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	CP	MT271630
221	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and mottlings	CP	MT271631
222	Adana-Turkey	Vein clearing	CP	MT271632
223	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and vein clearing	CP	MT271633
253	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mottlings	CP	MT271634
254	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and leaf deformation	CP	MT271635
268	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271636

274	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	CP	MT271637
278	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	CP	MT271638
360	Aydin-Turkey	Yellowing	CP	MT271639
3	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	NIa-Pro	MT271640
5	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	NIa-Pro	MT271641
48	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	NIa-Pro	MT271642
64	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271643
187	Hatay-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns and heavy chlorotic spots	NIa-Pro	MT271644
201	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	NIa-Pro	MT271645
216	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and mottlings	NIa-Pro	MT271646
221	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and mottlings	NIa-Pro	MT271647
222	Adana-Turkey	Vein clearing	NIa-Pro	MT271648
223	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and vein clearing	NIa-Pro	MT271649
225	Adana-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271650
226	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and mottlings	NIa-Pro	MT271651
228	Adana-Turkey	Mosaics, oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271652
229	Adana-Turkey	Vein clearing	NIa-Pro	MT271653
231	Adana-Turkey	Light mosaics	NIa-Pro	MT271654

232	Adana-Turkey	Mosaics, oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271655
239	Adana-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271656
241	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and mottlings	NIa-Pro	MT271657
242	Adana-Turkey	Vein clearing	NIa-Pro	MT271658
243	Adana-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271659
244	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and mottlings	NIa-Pro	MT271660
245	Adana-Turkey	Oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271661
247	Adana-Turkey	Yellowing and oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271662
252	Hatay-Turkey (Ornamental Pomegranate)	No symptoms	NIa-Pro	MT271663
257	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	NIa-Pro	MT271664
258	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	NIa-Pro	MT271665
260	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and mosaics	NIa-Pro	MT271666
261	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271667
265	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271668
266	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271669
267	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271670
270	Hatay-Turkey	Yellowing and oak-leaf patterns	NIa-Pro	MT271671

Table S4. Pairwise nucleotide sequence identity in the Nla-Pro gene between PeSV isolates.

Isolate	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	132	133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144	145	146	147	148	149	150	151	152	153	154	155	156	157	158	159	160	161	162	163	164	165	166	167	168	169	170	171	172	173	174	175	176	177	178	179	180	181	182	183	184	185	186	187	188	189	190	191	192	193	194	195	196	197	198	199	200
1	100	98	99	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	84	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1																																																																																																				